

NDAC/LO/018
1983 April 5

Pseudosolution and pseudocovariance
for least-squares problems with known null space

by L Lindegren

Let

$$\underline{Ax} = \underline{b} \quad (1)$$

be normal equations with a symmetric (n,n) -matrix $\underline{A}$ of rank $r = n-d < n$. The null space of $\underline{A}$ is the subspace of $\mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\mathbb{N} = \{\underline{w} \in \mathbb{R}^n: \underline{Aw} = \underline{0}\} \quad (2)$$

We shall consider least-squares problems where the rank defect (d) is a built-in and desirable property due to, for instance, unspecified coordinate origins or orientations. Assuming that the problem is otherwise well conditioned, the null space is then known *a priori*, i.e. we are able to specify d linearly independent vectors in $\mathbb{N}$:

$$\underline{w}_1, \underline{w}_2, \dots, \underline{w}_d \in \mathbb{N} \quad (3)$$

This is the case for the HIPPARCOS data analysis both in Step 1 (Set solution, $d = 1$) and Step 2 (PRS solution, $d = 6$); see Appendix. For such problems we call $\underline{x} = \underline{A}^+ \underline{b}$ the pseudosolution and $\underline{A}^+$ the pseudocovariance. Here $\underline{A}^+$ is the (Moore-Penrose) generalized inverse, which may be defined as follows. Let $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_r > \lambda_{r+1} = \dots = \lambda_n = 0$ be the eigenvalues of $\underline{A}$ ordered in non-increasing sequence and $\underline{e}_1, \dots, \underline{e}_n$ corresponding orthonormalized eigenvectors. Then

$$\underline{A} = \underline{E} \underline{\Lambda} \underline{E}' = (\underline{e}_1 \ \underline{e}_2 \ \dots \ \underline{e}_n) \text{diag}(\lambda_1 \ \lambda_2 \ \dots \ \lambda_n) (\underline{e}_1 \ \underline{e}_2 \ \dots \ \underline{e}_n)' \quad (4)$$

and

$$\underline{A}^+ = \underline{E} \underline{\Lambda}^+ \underline{E}' = \underline{E} \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{-1} \ \lambda_2^{-1} \ \dots \ \lambda_r^{-1} \ 0 \ \dots \ 0) \underline{E}' \quad (5)$$

If $\underline{E}$ and $\underline{\Lambda}$ are partitioned

$$\underline{E} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} \underline{U} & \underline{V} \\ \hline \underline{r} & \underline{d} \end{array} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\underline{\Lambda} = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} \underline{D} & \underline{0} \\ \hline \underline{0} & \underline{0} \end{array} \right) \begin{array}{l} \text{ } r \\ \text{ } d \end{array} \quad (7)$$

we find

$$\underline{A} = \underline{U}\underline{D}\underline{U}' \quad (8)$$

$$\underline{A}^+ = \underline{U}\underline{D}^{-1}\underline{U}' \quad (9)$$

The eigenvectors corresponding to a multiple eigenvalue are not uniquely defined, since any linear combination of them is also an eigenvector of the same eigenvalue. $\underline{V}$ may therefore be any set of orthonormal vectors in N , obtained e.g. by Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization of $\underline{w}_1, \dots, \underline{w}_d$:

$$\underline{V} = (\underline{v}_1 \quad \underline{v}_2 \quad \dots \quad \underline{v}_d); \quad (10)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \underline{v}_1 &= \underline{w}_1 \left| \underline{w}_1 \right|^{-1}, \\ \underline{v}_k &= \left[\underline{w}_k - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \underline{v}_j \underline{v}_j' \underline{w}_k \right] \left| \underline{w}_k - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \underline{v}_j \underline{v}_j' \underline{w}_k \right|^{-1}, \quad k = 2, \dots, d \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

The orthonormality of $\underline{E}$ ($\underline{E}\underline{E}' = \underline{E}'\underline{E} = \underline{I}_n$) implies the following relations between $\underline{U}$ and $\underline{V}$:

$$\underline{U}'\underline{U} = \underline{I}_r \quad (12a)$$

$$\underline{U}'\underline{V} = \underline{0}(r,d) \quad (12b)$$

$$\underline{V}'\underline{V} = \underline{I}_d \quad (12c)$$

$$\underline{U}\underline{U}' + \underline{V}\underline{V}' = \underline{I}_n \quad (12d)$$

In order to solve our least-squares problem by ordinary methods (Cholesky), we introduce a (d,n) -matrix $\underline{G}$ corresponding to the "observations"

$$\underline{Gx} = \underline{0} \quad (13)$$

The "fixed" normals

$$(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})\underline{x} = \underline{b} \quad (14)$$

are non-singular if the components in N of the row vectors of $\underline{G}$ are linearly independent. That is, the (d,d) -matrix $\underline{GV}$ must be non-singular:

$$\det(\underline{GV}) \neq 0 \quad (15)$$

The fixing equations (13) typically specify d simple coordinates, e.g. the abscissa of an origin star for the set solution or the positions and proper motions of $1\frac{1}{2}$ orientation stars for the PRS solution. Using (4) and $\underline{EE}' = \underline{I}_n$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G} &= \underline{E}\underline{\Lambda}\underline{E}' + \underline{E}\underline{E}'\underline{G}'\underline{G}\underline{E}\underline{E}' \\ &= \underline{E}(\underline{\Lambda} + \underline{E}'\underline{G}'\underline{G}\underline{E})\underline{E}' \\ &= \underline{E}\left[\underline{\Lambda} + (\underline{GU} \quad \underline{GV})'(\underline{GU} \quad \underline{GV})\right]\underline{E}' \\ &= \underline{E}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{D} + \underline{U}'\underline{G}'\underline{GU} & \underline{U}'\underline{G}'\underline{GV} \\ \underline{V}'\underline{G}'\underline{GU} & \underline{V}'\underline{G}'\underline{GV} \end{pmatrix}\underline{E}' \\ &= \underline{E}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_r & \underline{U}'\underline{G}' \\ \underline{0} & \underline{V}'\underline{G}' \end{pmatrix}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{D} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{I}_d \end{pmatrix}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_r & \underline{0} \\ \underline{GU} & \underline{GV} \end{pmatrix}\underline{E}' \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

It is seen that $\det(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G}) = \det^2(\underline{GV}) \prod_{i=1}^r \lambda_i$, proving that (15) is indeed the condition for non-singular $\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G}$. Inverting, we find

$$(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1} = \underline{E}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_r & \underline{0} \\ \underline{GU} & \underline{GV} \end{pmatrix}^{-1}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{D}^{-1} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{I}_d \end{pmatrix}\begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_r & \underline{U}'\underline{G}' \\ \underline{0} & \underline{V}'\underline{G}' \end{pmatrix}^{-1}\underline{E}' \quad (17)$$

from which

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{D}^{-1} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{I}_d \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_r & \underline{0} \\ \underline{G}\underline{U} & \underline{G}\underline{V} \end{pmatrix} \underline{E}'(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1} \underline{E} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{I}_r & \underline{U}'\underline{G}' \\ \underline{0} & \underline{V}'\underline{G}' \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \underline{U}' \\ \underline{G} \end{pmatrix} (\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1} (\underline{U} \quad \underline{G}') \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

or

$$\underline{D}^{-1} = \underline{U}'(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1}\underline{U} \quad (19a)$$

$$\underline{0}(r,d) = \underline{U}'(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1}\underline{G}' \quad (19b)$$

$$\underline{I}_d = \underline{G}(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1}\underline{G}' \quad (19c)$$

Inserting (19a) in (9) and using (12d) we finally get

$$\underline{A}^+ = (\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}')(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1}(\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}') \quad (20)$$

Pre-multiplying by $\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}'$ is such a central operation that we introduce a special notation,

$$\underline{\tilde{f}} = (\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}')\underline{f} \quad (21)$$

for arbitrary n-vector $\underline{f}$. Explicitly,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} c_k &= \sum_{j=1}^n V_{jk} f_j, \quad k = 1, \dots, d; \\ \tilde{f}_i &= f_i - \sum_{k=1}^d c_k V_{ik}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

showing that in-place computation of $\underline{\tilde{f}}$ is possible with very little extra storage besides $\underline{V}$.

Pseudosolution

Since the column vectors of $\underline{V}$ belong to the null space,

$$\underline{A}\underline{V} = \underline{0}(n,d) \quad (23)$$

Consequently, if (1) is consistent,

$$\underline{V}'\underline{b} = \underline{V}'\underline{Ax} = (\underline{AV})'\underline{x} = \underline{0} \quad (24)$$

and

$$\underline{\tilde{b}} = \underline{b} - \underline{VV}'\underline{b} = \underline{b} \quad (25)$$

The pseudosolution is therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{x} &= \underline{A}^+\underline{b} = (\underline{I} - \underline{VV}')(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1}(\underline{I} - \underline{VV}')\underline{b} \\ &= (\underline{I} - \underline{VV}')(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})^{-1}\underline{b} \\ &= \underline{\tilde{y}} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where $\underline{y}$ is the solution to the fixed normals

$$(\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G})\underline{y} = \underline{b} \quad (27)$$

The pseudosolution is thus obtained by (i) adding the "observations" (13) to the problem, (ii) solving the resulting ("fixed") equations, (iii) modifying the solution according to (22).

An interesting interpretation of the pseudosolution suggests itself if we include the orthogonalization of $\underline{W} = (\underline{w}_1 \ \underline{w}_2 \ \dots \ \underline{w}_d)$ in the procedure. Let $\underline{T}$ be a transformation [(d,d)-matrix] such that

$$\underline{V} = \underline{WT} \quad (28)$$

satisfies (12c). Then

$$\underline{T}'\underline{W}'\underline{WT} = \underline{I}_d \Leftrightarrow \underline{W}'\underline{W} = \underline{T}'^{-1}\underline{T}^{-1} \Leftrightarrow \underline{TT}' = (\underline{W}'\underline{W})^{-1} \quad (29)$$

and

$$\underline{VV}' = \underline{WTT}'\underline{W}' = \underline{W}(\underline{W}'\underline{W})^{-1}\underline{W}' \quad (30)$$

In terms of the fixed solution $\underline{y}$ and the non-normalized vectors $\underline{W}$, the pseudosolution is therefore

$$\tilde{\underline{y}} = \underline{y} - \underline{Wz} \quad (31)$$

where the d-vector $\underline{z}$ is the solution to the least-squares problem

$$\underline{Wz} \approx \underline{y} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \underline{z} = (\underline{W}'\underline{W})^{-1}\underline{W}'\underline{y} \quad (32)$$

Now in the PRS solution, for instance, the six vectors $\underline{w}_k$ in $\underline{W}$ may express the effects on the astrometric parameters of misorientations and uniform rotation about three orthogonal axes (see Appendix); then $\underline{z}$ gives the "average" misorientation and rotation of the fixed solution (with respect to *a priori* data) and the pseudosolution is simply the fixed solution corrected for these effects. The pseudosolution obviously satisfies

$$\underline{W}'\tilde{\underline{y}} = \underline{0} \quad (33)$$

i.e. no net misorientation or rotation.

Pseudocovariance

Let $\underline{i}_i$ denote the i :th column of $\underline{I}_n$, with elements $i_{ij} = \delta_{ij}$. A certain element of A^+ is then computed as

$$(\underline{A}^+)_{ij} = \underline{i}_i' \underline{A}^+ \underline{i}_j \quad (34)$$

Now let

$$\underline{A} + \underline{G}'\underline{G} = \underline{F}'\underline{F} \quad (35)$$

be the Cholesky factorization of the fixed normal equations matrix. With (20) we have then

$$\begin{aligned} (\underline{A}^+)_{ij} &= \underline{i}_i' (\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}') \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{F}'^{-1} (\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}') \underline{i}_j \\ &= \left[\underline{F}'^{-1} (\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}') \underline{i}_i \right]' \left[\underline{F}'^{-1} (\underline{I} - \underline{V}\underline{V}') \underline{i}_j \right] \\ &= (\underline{F}'^{-1} \underline{\tilde{i}}_i)' (\underline{F}'^{-1} \underline{\tilde{i}}_j) \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

In particular the pseudovariance of the i :th unknown is

$$(\underline{A}^+)_{ii} = \left| \underline{F}'^{-1} \tilde{\underline{i}}_i \right|^2 \quad (37)$$

For a conventional (non-singular) least-squares solution, the covariances are computed as

$$[(\underline{F}'\underline{F})^{-1}]_{ij} = (\underline{F}'^{-1} \tilde{\underline{i}}_i)' (\underline{F}'^{-1} \tilde{\underline{i}}_j) \quad (38)$$

i.e. by inserting $\tilde{\underline{i}}_i$ and $\tilde{\underline{i}}_j$ as right-hand sides (rhs), reducing (pre-multiplying by $\underline{F}'^{-1}$), and taking the scalar product. From (26)-(27) and (36) it is thus seen that computing the pseudosolution and/or pseudocovariance only requires the added capability of performing the $\tilde{}$ operation (22) on the rhs, before or after a conventional (fixed) solution. This in turn requires that the (n,d)-matrix $\underline{V}$ be computed and stored.

APPENDIX: Null space vectors for Step 1 and 2

Step 1 (Set solution)

For a set with m stars and M instrument parameters, the $n = m + M$ unknowns are (after elimination of frame attitudes; cf. NDAC/LO/016)

$$\underline{x} = \left(\begin{array}{c} \Delta \underline{U}_1 \\ \Delta \underline{U}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta \underline{U}_m \\ \Delta d_1 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta d_M \end{array} \right) \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} \left. \begin{array}{c} \Delta \underline{U}_1 \\ \Delta \underline{U}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta \underline{U}_m \end{array} \right\} \text{abscissa corrections} \\ \left. \begin{array}{c} \Delta d_1 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta d_M \end{array} \right\} \text{corrections to instrument parameters} \end{array} \right\} \quad (A.1)$$

If $\underline{x}$ is a solution of $\underline{Ax} = \underline{b}$, then $\underline{x} + s\underline{w}_1$ is also a solution for any scalar s, where

$$\underline{w}_1 = \underbrace{(1 \quad 1 \quad \dots \quad 1)}_m \quad \underbrace{(0 \quad \dots \quad 0)}_M \quad (A.2)$$

This is simply a shift of the abscissa zero point. Therefore $\underline{Aw}_1 = \underline{0}$ and

$\underline{w}_1$ belongs to the null space ($d = 1$). The normalized vector is

$$\underline{v}_1 = (m^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad m^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad m^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad 0 \quad \dots \quad 0)' \quad (\text{A.3})$$

and the $\sim$ operation (22) amounts to subtracting the average abscissa correction from the individual values. It is noted that the solution for the instrument parameters (and their covariances) are not affected.

Step 2 (PRS solution)

With m primary stars, five astrometric unknowns per star, and M global parameters (e.g. relativity parameters), $n = 5m + M$ and $d = 6$. The unknowns are

$$\underline{x} = \left(\begin{array}{c} \Delta\alpha_1 \cos \delta_1 \\ \Delta\delta_1 \\ \Delta\mu_{\alpha 1} \cos \delta_1 \\ \Delta\mu_{\delta 1} \\ \Delta\Pi_1 \\ \Delta\alpha_2 \cos \delta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta\Pi_m \\ \Delta p_1 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta p_M \end{array} \right) \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} \text{astrometric parameters} \\ \\ \\ \text{global parameters} \end{array} \right\} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

In terms of the six components of a general misorientation ($\underline{\epsilon}_g$) and rotation ($\underline{\omega}_g$) with respect to the provisional system, the variation of unknowns is [NDAC Proposal, (A.15.2)-(A.15.3)]

$$\Delta \underline{x} = \underline{W} \left(\begin{array}{c} \underline{\epsilon}_g \\ \underline{\omega}_g \end{array} \right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

with

$\underline{W} =$

(A.6)

$$\begin{pmatrix}
 \sin \delta_1 \cos \alpha_1 & \sin \delta_1 \sin \alpha_1 & -\cos \delta_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 -\sin \alpha_1 & \cos \alpha_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & \sin \delta_1 \cos \alpha_1 & \sin \delta_1 \sin \alpha_1 & -\cos \delta_1 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sin \alpha_1 & \cos \alpha_1 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 \sin \delta_2 \cos \alpha_2 & \sin \delta_2 \sin \alpha_2 & -\cos \delta_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sin \alpha_m & \cos \alpha_m & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0
 \end{pmatrix}$$

If the PRS equations are truly independent of the provisional system of positions and proper motions used, we must have $\underline{AW} = \underline{0}$. That the columns of $\underline{W}$ in (A.6) are linearly independent is easily seen; indeed they are almost orthogonal if the stars are uniformly distributed over the celestial sphere:

$$\underline{W}'\underline{W} \approx \text{diag} \left(\frac{2m}{3} \quad \frac{2m}{3} \quad \frac{2m}{3} \quad \frac{2m}{3} \quad \frac{2m}{3} \quad \frac{2m}{3} \right) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Again it can be noted that the parallax corrections ($\Delta\Pi_i$) and global parameters (Δp_i), and their variances, are not affected by the $\sim$ operation (since the corresponding rows of $\underline{W}$ contain only zeroes); they are the same for the fixed solution and the pseudosolution.